

Emotional Intelligence, Soft Power and the Value of Dialogical Relationships in Intra/Interpersonal Communication

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Abstract

This paper is going to look at the potential intersection of issues of Emotional Intelligence and soft power. This paper has two main purposes, to shed light on the need for emotional intelligence as soft power, and to view intra/interpersonal relationships from a dialogic perspective. It is going to shed light on the importance of embracing change and ambiguity to retain self-awareness. Additionally, the paper is going to look at one of the major components of emotional intelligence, which is personal magnetism.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence; soft power; dialogic; intra/interpersonal; change; personal magnetism

1. Introduction

Emotional intelligence is an area of interest that drew in intense attention from professional, scientific, and lay factions. From neuroscience to culture to mainstream culture, EI developed into a concept of concern that continues to evolve. It has been generally associated in the literature with adaptive skills on personal and social levels (Mayer, J. D., Salovey, P. and Caruso, D. R.)¹. In addition, EI is linked to one's mental abilities of perceiving appraise, and their accurate ability in expressing emotions. It is the knack to invest in emotion relevant concepts so as to promote one's personal and professional growth, create a healthy state of mind, and function smoothly in socially related encounters².

EI is achieved through a person's ability to identify, comprehend, administer, and practice a process of reasoning using emotions. "This soft skill is becoming more sought after by employers. With today's focus on company culture and teamwork, emotional intelligence is a critical component to building high performing teams" (Evans)³. Thus, "emotional intelligence is the ability to understand, use, and manage your own emotions in positive ways to relieve stress, communicate effectively, and empathize" (Melinda)⁴

Notably, the last two decades have been marked by the changing nature of the structure of global power. The world is shifting towards softer means of intelligence and intelligent power exercise, knowledge is the new power system⁵. The whole concept has transformed and has gained a new form known as "soft Power", the term was coined by Harvard University Professor Joseph Nye in his book *Bound to Lead: the changing nature of American Power*, which was published in 1990. In addition, the prominent American analyst Arquilla, J. is one of the advocates for the need of changing perspectives to power. In the current global information age, success is not always dependent on whose army wins, but

on whose story wins; a belief long held and often echoed in the works of Joseph Nye. I believe that the paradigm shift in today's world focuses on the effectiveness of soft power, and the value of communicating a winning intersubjective global narrative rather than imposing one via violent means. The focus is on dialogic relation, the peaceful practice of communicative processes and power relations.

Significantly, in politics and in the international diplomacy spectrum, soft power refers to the ability to attract and create an image of fascination in the international arena. It is based on diplomacy rather than coercion and the practice of the hard power appeal. Unlike hard power, soft power is concerned with determining the preferences of others and later on shaping them, all through softer means of appeal and attraction.⁶

This paper is going to view the dialogic relations potentially held among emotional intelligence and soft power, especially within intra/interpersonal contexts. This study is jumpstarted by looking at the theory of dialogism, and its influences on the self, identity and the other. Followed by a critical dialogic analogy of emotional intelligence and soft power. The paper than will continue and deal with the importance of embracing change self-awareness. Finally, shed the light on personal magnetism as an essential emotional intelligence component.

2. Method

This paper mainly relies on critical and textual analysis. The paper provides a theoretical framework to the underdeveloped issues of emotional intelligence, soft power, and dialogic relationships within intra and interpersonal relationships.

3. Dialogism, the Self, Identity and the Other

Bakhtin's theory of dialogism helps one establish relationships between culture, language, and the self. It is an explanatory mechanism to intrapersonal and interpersonal communication, and an approach that helps to develop culture, language and identity as interactive and intercultural practices. On the other hand,

life essentially consists of dialogue, whether on a personal or group levels. The masses and elite alike experience dialogue and engage in dialogic discourse.

Dialogism is concerned with the creative processes of creating communication and forming one's personal identity through intrapersonal discourse. The inner speech we normally call *thought*, plays a primordial role in shaping one's identity. Thanks to works of Bakhtin, dialogism was shaped to answer questions of human consciousness. Therefore, it can be assumed that human consciousness relies on intra and interpersonal communication within a dialogic context.

To illustrate, dialogism deals with creating an utterance that is responsive towards another utterance. Understanding and replying to an utterance during a dialogue, means that one must alter their thinking and mental processes of internal dialogue to better listen and reply to the addressee. The space, spirit of the times, state of the arts, ethics, and the developed social common sense are all primary to the creation of the utterance⁷. Thus, the dialogic relationship is never isolated from its surrounding, it's a responsive reaction to the space and what's adjoining, as well as to the utterances created by the other. Nothing is created in isolation; everything is created through an 'inter-influencing' process.

One's dialogic relationship is majorly believed to be influenced by the other according to communication and dialogic theories. No individual creates a speech during a communication event without the use of the other's words, not even when a person is engaging in an intrapersonal communication in total solitude. There is always an echo of previous utterances that shape a person's current state of mind; and thus, the railroad of the thought processes to come. In other words, the other's utterance/language are used as the thinking processes take place, and as the speech is uttered. We are influenced by what we hear. Medina, J (2005) further illustrates the importance of the dialogic relationship taking place, especially through language, and refers that:

According to Humboldt, it is essential for an adequate understanding of language that we recognize that the web of language is being perpetually recreated in speech, that is, continuously extended, altered, and reconfigured in our linguistic performances and practices. As he famously put it, language is first and foremost *energeia*, not *ergon*, an activity, not a product. There are indeed products of our linguistic activities, but these tentative and ever-changing fruits of our practices are webs that we weave as we go and can never amount to a finished and complete system. (Medina)⁸

In this case, we are either at the top of the power relations pyramid or herd by the communication received. It is a stuck loop carefully orchestrated by some divine power to never cease to stop. The human mind is just like an intelligent system that never stops learning new utterances and engaging in new sets of commands within programmed loops. However, unlike intelligent systems, humans have the power of emotions and self-consciousness.

4. Emotional Intelligence as Soft Power

Regarding Soft Power, the term Soft Power has been widely attributed to Joseph Nye. It is a term deeply rooted in one's ability to persuade and brand themselves to attract the other. I believe that it is also attached with one's ability to master their own emotions, and to master the art of emotion-oriented communication. Not in the sense that one must be emotional and to make emotions the center of attention, but to be able to control the state of their emotions to their own gain based on the situation they encounter. This leads us to a power combination of emotional intelligence and soft power.

In soft power leadership, the two key influence and power resources comprise of one's personal qualities as a leader and one's communication skills. Combined with Emotional intelligence, it creates a projection of self-mastery and discipline, it

also showcases the power of empathy which allows a leader to project their passions and softly attract the other. Thus, emotional intelligence (EI) might be an exercise of soft power, where one is in total control of their emotions and is also totally aware of the other's emotions.

Vis-à-vis EI, it is a deeply rooted practice in one's ability to interact effectively, empathize with others, alleviate tension, overcome difficulties, and defuse conflict⁹. All of which are essential elements to succeed both on a personal and professional levels. Having an excellent skillset of EI would lead to the assumptions that EI would allow the individual to engage in:

- Offering a meaningful message as communication processes take place.
- Relating well to colleagues and customers within a certain environment.
- Establishing and sharing smooth relations with others.
- Getting information they need smoothly and without tension.
- Explaining matters easily, clearly, and speaking to the hearts and minds of the other.
- Becoming more successful in their careers and interpersonal relationships.
- Displaying more positive/productive relationship with others.
- Improving their own academic and professional performances.
- Improving their own personal effectiveness and intrapersonal communication skills.

Thus, EI is not only a mechanism to acquire power over the other, but it is also concerned with discipline and establishing power around one's own self. It helps individual better establish a dialogic understanding over themselves, the other, and

the situations they encounter. Therefore, EI skills could be viewed as the ground base for one's soft skills competencies and personal growth. In other words, emotional intelligence is the basis over which competencies of soft skills are built upon.

Emotional intelligence is the ability to differentiate between diverse emotions and recognize and understand them. Daniel Goleman (1995) attributed due importance to Emotional Intelligence, he viewed that it could be of even more value than IQ. For instance, I would argue that cognitive skills help you get the job, but emotional skills help you grow and nurture in the job. Meaning that one's soft skills matter more than the hard skills they possess, it is your ability to intelligently communicate with the others that matter, how you brand yourself, and how you decide the way the others see you that makes the cutting-edge difference. It is your ability to use the power of EI that decides where you are at your personal/professional state and where you would potentially go.

The implementation of EI could be broken down into five key concepts as suggested by Goleman: Self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, empathy, and social skills (Goleman, D. 1995 and 1998). All of which are essential elements not only to EI but also to the acquiring of the soft power it creates. It harnesses one's abilities to think rationally, motivate positive behaviors, and stimulate the ability to solve issues creatively and critically. Thus, establishing a skillset that allows one to make reasonable decisions and become excellent decision makers.

EI is of an immense importance in effective dialogic processes, whether ones occurring at the self or occurring at the social/cultural levels. For instance, an excellent implementation of EI skills is a key factor in achieving academic and professional success. In a busy and fast world, especially during the COVID 19 pandemic, we are drowned and driven by finishing tasks and thinking about the next steps, which consequently results in emotional detachment. Accordingly, the

individual falls to a state of mind where they lose attachment with their emotions; thus, it creates intrapersonal and social tensions. In order to delimit this stage, it is important to implement the Goleman Five Key elements of emotional intelligence. As a result, one will better understand their state of mind, the state of their emotions, and how to delimit negativity resulting from detachment. A good implementation of EI and good practice of social intelligence results in better communication and conflict management at the intra and interpersonal levels (Petrovici and Dobrescu)¹⁰.

To conclude, the dialogic nature of EI and soft power could be seen as the 49th law of power¹¹. It permits the individual to indulge in a process of self-discovery, to reach a state of emotional awareness, to be in sync with one's identity, and to be in control over the dialogic processes with the other.

5. Change, Self-Awareness and Framing

It is deeply rooted in psychology that one's self perception is a comfort zone, which is most of time protected at all costs. Nonetheless, evaluating our internal standards and values is inevitable if one wishes to better understand the self; thus, one becomes more accepting of the undoubtable need for change. Embracing a healthy amount of ambiguity through change would help individual gain self-control over stressful situations. Hence, stressful situations are an outcome of one's inability to let go of commonly internalized beliefs, which thus causes an inevitable crisis (Wakeman)¹².

The idea of change; therefore, is a deeply rooted concept in Reality Based Leadership. The individual must work on to delimit drama and learn to accept the need for change as it is. Change is linked to the present; an individual must not be trapped in the shadows of the past. One must be self-aware and gain self-control operating in the present, instead of being confined to past conditions. As Walkman, C (2010) assets:

There is a lot of big talk about leadership in the corporate world these days. Phrases like “engagement,” “building trust,” “succession planning,” and “employee development” get bandied about. But from what I have seen, the amount of talk is inversely proportional to the leadership. Reality-Based Leaders are different. They are less talk, more action. They are willing to forgive, to refrain from judging others, and to serve. Reality-Based Leadership is humility in action, and humility requires that you give your ego a rest. Everyone has heard of the ego, and you might even think that a little ego is healthy, necessary, even, to lead others and succeed.¹³

Just as self-awareness, one must also develop a social awareness that can lead them to success. Being aware of the self and the other requisites a high level of empathy. For instance, practicing social empathy is concerned with putting one’s shoe in the other, understanding the hearts and minds of people, and developing an outside perspective to how the other sees the world. If I am able to see the world through someone else’s eye, I am going to be able to master the art of EI.

One might ask: What is the difference between self-awareness and emotional intelligence? – There is not a major difference between the two, because both leads automatically to the other. For instance, self-awareness refers to one’s ability to identify, distinguish and comprehend their sets of emotions; thus, it is a critical skill to emotional intelligence. It goes beyond only identifying one’s emotions. It is about a person being aware of the consequences and outcomes of their actions, moods, attitudes, and emotions on other people or groups of people. Therefore, self-awareness is a basic requirement for emotional intelligence.

EI is also rooted in non-verbal communication, not all emotions are expressed through utterances, one must be able to decipher physical cues (facial expressions, gestures, posture ...etc). For instance, Ekman, P.¹⁴ views facial expressions as a primary canvas to express emotions none-verbally; and thus, reading facial

expressions is vital. Therefore, the information one is able to acquire through facial expressions stimulates efficient interpersonal behavior, and consequently maximize social outcomes (McArthur, Z. and Baron, M.)¹⁵

Through outside cues, one will be able to develop a perception of the other's inner state. One must be on the look for possible responsive reactions. Thus, anticipation is another central component to one's self-awareness, it is the fine line between one's self and the other. As Bakhtin illustrates (Caryl and Michael)¹⁶:

From the very beginning, the utterance is constructed while taking into account possible responsive reactions, for whose sake, in essence, it is actually created. As we know, the role of others for whom the utterance is constructed is extremely great. We have already said that the role of these others, for whom my thought becomes actual thought for the first time (and thus for my own self as well) is not that of passive listeners, but of active participants in speech communication. From the very beginning, the speaker expects a response from them, an active responsive understanding. The entire utterance is constructed, as it were, in anticipation of encountering this response.

Therefore, in order to account for the other in practical yet thoughtful ways, one must engage in processes of framing and categorizing. According to Rothman, S¹⁷, normative and analytical framing are viewed as the major tools for soft power practice. *Meaning* is constructed and put on forth through dialogic persuasion where actors take the task of clear-cut communication processes. Normative framing deals with an issue from an emotional and/or moral perspective, while analytical framing is concerned with causal relations, It is a process of analyzing events in order to discover the causes and effects (Adoui, A.).

Normative framing strategy, as suggested by Rothman, is a means to delve into morals or emotions of the receiver. For instance, we could talk about moral framing. Where one relies on influencing the other via appealing to their own

norms, all the while having the end goal in mind. Framing; thus, is based on appealing to the views of the other, and planning based on one's objectives, while finding the middle grounds along the way¹⁸.

Emotional appeal on the other hand is one of the major used strategies in all forms of communication (interpersonal, intercultural, political ...ec). There are various ways through which to convince and appeal to someone emotionally. For instance, organizations such as the UN, Green Peace and Doctors without Borders use images, videos, sounds, and share stories that plead to the receiver's emotions. Nonetheless, creating a framing strategy would not be successful without proper analytical framing of all the variables put in place.

Stone (1989) suggests that analytical framing relies on the relationships of causality in a story set¹⁹. There has to be a process of SWOT analysis, defining strengths and opportunities, but also the potential weaknesses and threats. Rothman (2011) referred to this as defining the points of strength and grant credit or point out the causes of harm and endow responsibility. One is invited to use all information at hand so that to support and legitimize their own views (Jasanoff)²⁰.

Emotional Intelligence remains a key ingredient in embracing change and the process of development. Emotional self-awareness, a component of EI; thus, is not an overnight process and it is not something you achieve and it is done for. In fact, change and progress remain a cyclic process that does not stop. According to Goleman, D.²¹:

Emotional Self-Awareness isn't something that you achieve once and then you're done with it. Rather, every moment is an opportunity to either be self-aware or not. It is a continual endeavor, a conscious choice to be self-aware. The good news is that the more you practice it, the easier it becomes. Research by my colleague and friend Richard Davidson suggests that one way to become more

self-aware is to check in with your sensory experience regularly, and shift your behavior accordingly.

One must be in constant intellectual progress of reviewing and recognizing emotions and understand their impact on one's performance. Individuals must detach themselves and re-experience a particular state of mind, identify strengths and weaknesses, and develop a better strategy.

6. Personal Magnetism as Dialogic Persuasion

Personal magnetism is concerned with inspiring fascination and loyalty (Nye, J.)²². It is the process of appealing to the other's self interest in order to persuade. It is not related to deception in fact, not at all, it simply is concerned with mirroring someone else's interests to find common grounds where both parties engage in a win-win situation. It is used interchangeably with terms such as personal appeal, attraction and charisma, all of which indicate a personal attractiveness or interestingness that enables an individual to influence others through a soft power manner (Adoui, A.)²³.

In international relations for instance, soft power is used for dialogic persuasion, state leaders use personal magnetism to acquire power. In turn, soft power in international relations theory is a measurement of influence, a reflection of victory, and a reflection of control over resources. Thus, personal magnetism is overly measured by the power of attraction and influence one holds. Both of which are modified and defined by an actor's ability to adapt their behavior to that of the other. The key point [...] here is the notion of the vitality put on understanding the conditions under which an actor's capabilities result in influence. Soft power is conditioned by understanding the different role players and key factors, understanding their capabilities of influence, creates what could be called an action plan to determine the type of soft power necessary to achieve the objective of attraction and influence.

Meaning that, the exercise of soft power's personal magnetism heavily relies on calculated planning. It is not a hit or miss process. One must be aware of the accruing situations, the space and culture, and the causal relationships among the various actors and factors present. Thus, one must practice the power of emotional intelligence in the process of creating their personal action plan model. It is a slower, surer, and much further civilized way of implementing influence than obscene force. The essence of personal magnetism practice in soft power is that our recipients are free to say no. We do not pressure, intimidate or manipulate them. We engage in processes of persuasion and coopting by establishing common grounds and charming the other's self-interest. Thus, both sides eventually gain, although not necessarily on equal footing.

Personal magnetism relies heavily on one's emotional self-awareness. In this regard, Goleman, D. (2021) illustrates that:

Emotional Self-Awareness is the ability to understand your own emotions and their effects on your performance. You know what you are feeling and why — and how it helps or hurts what you are trying to do. You sense how others see you and so align your self-image with a larger reality. You have an accurate sense of your strengths and limitations, which gives you a realistic self-confidence. It also gives you clarity on your values and sense of purpose, so you can be more decisive when you set a course of action. As a leader, you can be candid and authentic, speaking with conviction about your vision.

Thus, personal magnetism relies on one's ability to shape themselves in accordance to the space and spirit of the times they are encountered with. It is concerned with aligning one's image to the general feel and creating links where one is able to speak to others through one's personality traits. It is one's ability to have others look up to them, through authenticity, and candidness. One must be

able to engage in dialogic relations based on a give and take paradigm, and the ability to be outspoken and candid about one's convictions and visions.

Emotional self-awareness is a gateway to understanding how you are performing; and thus, acquiring the pieces of data that will help you understand your strengths and weaknesses. Consequently, it will assist you in shaping and reshaping the sense of your-self and your image. It will give you a clear perspective in regard to you intrapersonal and interpersonal relations (Petrovici and Dobrescu)²⁴.

Goleman, D. (2021) pointed a prominent real-world example that hampers one's ability to engage in fruitful and honest interpersonal relations. For instance:

Consider this real-world example: The chief tech officer at an innovation incubator is a bully, but he doesn't know it. He's very good at what he does except when it comes to managing people. He plays favorites. He tells people what to do. He doesn't listen. He freezes people out that he doesn't like. If you confront him with a specific incident, he denies it. He pins the blame on someone else and gets angry with them. Or he tells you that you're the problem. Last I heard, he was about to be fired.

The tech officer in the example let their ego take the lead, they lack emotional self-awareness. They are too self-absorbed to see the world around them. They are too engrossed in themselves to see potential in others, and to engage with others in meaningful relations. Ego is the scariest trap one would fall into during any process. It renders the processes of attaining emotional intelligent skills and soft power futile. Ego fuels feelings of victimhood, creates low morale, and creates emotional waste. In addition, the inability to control one's emotions and lack of self-awareness makes the person seems incompetent, has poor self-control, and lacks leadership traits.

There has always been an internal battle of ego and reality in one's mind. Therefore, this necessitates one to invest in taming their ego to healthy degrees, and to rely on reality as the driving force of their self-awareness and actions to

come. Walkman, C.²⁵ put a finger on the need to control one's ego praised the need for realism, she stated that:

The thing is, we all have one. The ego is the part of our psyche that mediates self-identity and experience, and ego is instrumental in governing how we adapt to reality. Having an ego is nothing to feel bad about. Yet it is also important to recognize that one of the ego's main functions is to generate emotional waste. It is an unreliable narrator of experience because its judging nature separates us from others. It delights in the drama it can create. The Buddha called the ego the source of all suffering.

Reality, in contrast, is your friend. It's the pal who will give it to you straight. The highest-quality data comes from reality. If you rely on reality to guide your decisions, it won't let you down. It gives you reliable, real-time information about what works, what doesn't, and where you need to grow next.

Thus, we must be generally aware of our state of mind and to engage in embracing self-awareness through reality. Ego operates out of self-interest; it seeks validation and approval at any cost so as to seem *right*. Therefore, one must not deny this stage, and not mistake it with confidence. Confidence reflects one's belief in their abilities, but ego is about avoiding self-reflection. Engaging in dialogic processing of self-reflection is a primordial move in attaining or obtaining personal magnetism skills (Nye; Wakeman). Therefore, great leaders have a developed sense of self-awareness and emotional intelligence skills. They are able to bring the best of themselves, others, and create positive and motivating emotional climate in their surroundings. Personal magnetism or charisma is the ultimate soft power.

A prominent example of the practice of personal magnetism and soft power is the recent elections in Morocco, mainly with the National Rally of Liberation - known as RNI. RNI won the elections thanks to digitalization and going beyond traditional election campaigns Morocco majorly knew. Mr. Akhnouch, the head of the party, was able to show, through using the digital space to promote himself

during the campaign period; great skills of leadership, personal magnetism, practicing a coopting dialog, and using a clear-cut soft power that allowed him to lead a successful election campaign, for which his party eventually won. Mr. Akhnouch was able to lead a politically correct campaign, which spoke to all Moroccans. He did not engage in identity, religious, and belonging topics, and he did not at any stage create friction or name called any of the parties. In fact, as the party won, he called all other parties without any exception to join hands and create better governing together. Thus, I believe that during his campaign Mr. Akhnouch skillfully showed great emotional intelligence and soft skills awareness. The leadership of Mr. Akhnouch within the RNI and during the strategic campaign that has been in planning over the past four years, shows the potential – especially within the Moroccan context – of practicing the skillset of EI and soft power. The move to digitalization and the passing of soft messages all over social media and traffic generating websites, allowed the Mr. Akhnouch campaign to go above and beyond. RNI was able to win more votes, engage new voters in the process of electing, singlehandedly create the majority within the government, and sustain a good reputation all through the campaign.

7. Conclusion

In brief, despite the underdeveloped nature of dialogic EI and soft power in the literature, and the absence of these issues interconnectedly in academia, one is able to draw major conclusions thanks to the variables available. This paper is an invitation to draw attention to this issue within academia and especially in the communication and political communication studies.

This paper looked at and intersected the issues of EI and soft power especially through the scope of dialogic intrapersonal and interpersonal communication. The study tackled the dialogic theory and its influence on issues of the self, identity and the other. The conversation continued in the same vein and looked at the

intersection of emotional intelligence and soft skills. Then the study shed light on the importance of embracing change and ambiguity to retain self-awareness. Finally, the paper looked at one of the major components of emotional intelligence, which is also essential for soft power, personal magnetism could be viewed as a common element between both spectrums.

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